

CZU: 378.014.542:378.126

THE INTELLECTUAL OUTPUT OF STRATEGIC PLANNING IN THE SERVICE OF QUALITY VOCATIONAL EDUCATION

Viorica GORAȘ-POSTICĂ, Svetlana CHEPTANARI, Mariana NEGREAN**

Moldova State University

**Tiraspol State University*

The present study includes a praxiological research on the process and results of strategic planning in a vocational medical institution in the Republic of Moldova. As the intellectual product obtained is a quality one, meeting several relevant indicators, we decided to analyze and disseminate this good practice. The theoretical landmarks approached focus on the current rigors of strategic management in the field of education, aiming at contributing to solving priority problems in a specific professional context. The development of the educational institution from the perspective of quality, in general, and of the actors of education expectations, in particular, guides the organizational management, with its classic functions of planning, organization, coordination and control-evaluation.

Keywords: *strategic planning, intellectual product, strategic development plan, educational institution, students, teachers and managers, quality education, professional training.*

PRODUSUL INTELLECTUAL AL PLANIFICĂRII STRATEGICE ÎN SERVICIUL EDUCAȚIEI PROFESIONALE DE CALITATE

Studiul de față include o cercetare cu caracter praxiologic asupra procesului și rezultatelor planificării strategice într-o instituție vocațională de profil medical din Republica Moldova. Deoarece produsul intelectual obținut este unul de calitate, întrunind mai mulți indicatori relevanți, am decis să analizăm și să diseminăm această bună practică. Reperetele teoretice abordate se axează pe rigorile curente ale managementului strategic în domeniul educației, având ca țintă contribuția la soluționarea unor probleme prioritare dintr-un context profesional specific. Dezvoltarea instituției de învățământ din perspectiva calității, în general, și a așteptărilor actorilor educației, în particular, ghidează managementul organizațional, cu funcțiile sale clasice de planificare, organizare, coordonare și control-evaluare.

Cuvinte-cheie: *planificare strategică, produs intelectual, plan de dezvoltare strategică, instituție de învățământ, elevi, cadre didactice și manageriale, educație de calitate, pregătire profesională.*

Introduction

It has already become axiomatic that in today's world, which is in a continuous change and in an accelerated and technological development, it is inconceivable that an institution in any field can evolve without having in its organizational and functional management, the *strategic planning* process. The intellectual product of strategic planning is *the strategic plan*, which is the document through which the management team communicates to the institution the objectives, actions and processes that will lead to the achievement of the established objectives, the people and resources involved, the expected results, the changes and adjustments that occur along the way.

In our study we aimed to analyze some main aspects of the strategic development plan [1], capitalized at the Center of Excellence in Medicine and Pharmacy "Raisa Pacalo"/ CEMF. This College is a public institution of medical vocational education, which prepares specialists at integrated professional programs, in accordance with the National Framework of Qualifications level 3, 4 and 5 of the Republic of Moldova, approved by Government Decision no.1016 of 23.11.2017 and the Nomenclature of professional training fields, specialties and qualifications for post-secondary and non-tertiary post-secondary technical vocational education, approved by Government Decision no.853 of 14.12.2015. According to its mission, CEMF is a post-secondary and post-secondary non-tertiary technical vocational education institution, which develops a quality medical vocational education, based on democratic, general-human values, responsibility, fairness, partnership, performance in the training of competent specialists in the field of medicine and pharmacy, who will show professionalism, ethical-moral qualities and perseverance in ensuring the quality of medical services provided to the population. For the achievement of this mission, effective and qualitative strategic planning is crucial, which will provide educational actors with feasible and credible products for current activity, but also for long-term development.

Theoretical framework

It is widely recognized that the strategic plan (SDP) contains all the fundamental elements through which the organization, functioning and long-term evolution of the organization is designed, as well as objectives, activities aimed at achieving them, people involved, resources involved, people and responsibilities, expected results. The fundamental relationship between *the strategic plan* and *strategic planning* is that strategic planning identifies, develops and establishes the elements contained in the strategic plan, which is in fact a product of the strategic planning process [Cf. 2]. It is an intellectual product that must meet advanced quality rigors, in order to ensure the quality and efficiency of the organization's activity, and, in our case, the educational process.

The Business Dictionary defines strategic planning as “a systematic process of protecting the desired future and ‘translating’ this vision into goals and a series of measures to achieve these goals. Unlike long-term planning (which begins with the current state and sets the path by which the estimated needs in the future are realized/met), strategic planning begins with the desired end (vision) and begins to work from the current state to achieve the vision. Compared to tactical planning (e.g. for example) (which focuses on achieving limited interim objectives through the use of predetermined means), strategic planning takes a broader approach and is more flexible in achieving the means” [3].

The development process of the educational institution involves a different approach that ensures the functionality of the management system of the institution by creating and maintaining the educational environment favorable to quality training by applying the documents corresponding to the current conceptual - normative framework. The development activities, as mentioned in the paper *Strategic planning versus operational planning*, are similar to those of research: *hypothesis – testing – conclusions – correcting hypotheses or setting new standards*. The operating activities and their results are evaluated on the basis of existing standards, and the activities and results aimed at development are carried out on the basis of the indicators set out in the strategic objectives. This necessarily requires reflection, which helps to identify the causes of successes and/or failures, to launch new solutions [4, p.9-10]. But at the same time, the activities of an institution cannot be strictly divided into two categories, since there is a close link between operation and development, this allows the formation of a state of transition, that of *developing the operation*, the purpose of which involves improving the aspects and directions that allow a better functioning of the institution. The achievement of the development activities through innovation is an indicator of the “maturity” of the institution and of the management team at the same time. The function-development tenderness contains one more valuable aspect. While the development activities have enjoyed success, we are convinced that the methods, processes, technologies used have proven their efficiency and, therefore, contribute to ensuring the quality of the educational services offered by the educational institution, which will be institutionalized and standardized. Thus, they will be transformed into activities that ensure operation.

Several models of the strategic planning process are described in the literature. Following the model proposed by G.Deeb (2018), for a successful strategy that wants to achieve success, the first vital steps for the development and implementation of the strategy are outlined:

1. *Assessing trends in industry, competition and customers.*
2. *Conducting the SWOT analysis regarding the organization's activity*
3. *Defining the vision and the mission.*
4. *Defining the strategic objectives of the organization.*
5. *Setting goals at department level.*
6. *Establishing the resources needed to achieve the strategic objectives* [5].

All the elements referred to in the preceding paragraphs may be gathered, at this stage, in a *strategic*, centralised plan with an organisational structure and a well-defined budget for each activity included in the objectives formulated.

Therefore, the development of the institution is one of the main concerns of the management team and is not found only in the SDP, because it contains the decisions of the institution regarding the development directions, the changes to be operated and the qualitative and quantitative expectations for a determined period of time (3-5 years). Simultaneously with the implementation of the SDP, the institution is in the process of continuously searching for future development opportunities. Therefore, operational plans must also contain the development options inherently. Ultimately, “... In the era of knowledge and information with which we are contemporaries, project and design as a process have become emblematic concepts, strategic planning is imposed not only as a vital necessity for the development of different entities, as legislative-procedural and

institutional normativity, but also as a functional preventive-resolution normativity” (Cf. Const. Cucos, Apud 6, p.17).

Praxiological framework. Case study

Quality management

In the strategic planning process at CEMF “Raisa Pacalo”, the management team starts from the axioms that quality management is a guarantor of educational success, and Quality is always the result of an intelligence effort. Quality in education designates a complex of principles and practices that cross the entire educational environment, in all its components, oriented towards obtaining superior results, related to standards and to satisfying the needs, expectations of the beneficiaries of education. Quality assurance in CEMF “Raisa Pacalo” involved new institutional roles, which are specified in the external functioning documents of the relevant ministries and ANACEC. The implementation of quality management in CEMF “Raisa Pacalo” is carried out on the basis of the International Standard ISO 29990:2010, which was adopted as a Moldovan standard SM ISO 29990:2016 on 05.07.2016. The international standard has guided the international practice and provided methodological support regarding the successful realization of a quality management system.

The Quality Management System (QMS), implemented in the institution since 2015, is reflected in the Internal Quality Evaluation Strategy, based on a policy, an organizational structure and procedures that allow the monitoring, evaluation and continuous improvement of the quality of the institution's activity, which correspond to the requirements of the Quality Management Guide in technical vocational education in the country. The principles of ensuring the quality of educational services, the methodology of quality management, the structures involved in quality assurance and the procedures for ensuring the educational efficiency in the institution are correlated with the national, international standards and defined in the Functioning Regulation of the internal evaluation and quality assurance commission. The purpose of the CEMF Quality Management System Manual “Raisa Pacalo” is to ensure, monitor, compatibility and evaluate the quality of educational services and other services offered by the institution with national and international standards in the field.

The Internal Evaluation and Quality Assurance Commission (IEQAC) has ensured the monitoring, compatibility and evaluation of the quality of the educational services and other services offered by the institution with the national and international standards in the field, developing, coordinating and applying procedures to ensure the transparency of internal quality evaluation processes, implementing performance indicators as tools for validating the achievement of the requirements defined by the reference standards at system level.

The policy of ensuring and continuously improving the quality in the institution focuses on:

- design and implementation of the quality management system at the level of all subdivisions of the Center of Excellence (CE) in medicine and pharmacy “Raisa Pacalo”;
- appointment of persons responsible for ensuring the quality management system at the level of institution, education sections, departments, household;
- conducting various sociological surveys with pupils, teachers, economic agents, parents;
- permanent study of the labour market;
- adaptation of the existing teaching-learning-evaluation technologies to the requirements of the labour market.

In this context, the implementation of quality management has the following benefits:

- ensuring a better correlation of the educational services offered by the Centre of Excellence with the requirements of the beneficiaries and other interested parties;
- permanent improvement of the quality of educational services offered by the institution;
- developing a culture of quality within the Centre of Excellence and ensuring a real protection of the interests of the beneficiaries and other stakeholders in the services offered by the institution;
- implementation of a system of internal evaluation of the quality of teaching and external evaluation processes, in order to certify the compliance of these processes with national standards;
- clarity in assuming the responsibilities of the Centre of Excellence's collaborators in terms of ensuring the quality of educational services;
- ensuring transparency in the way the Centre of Excellence uses the financial resources allocated to achieve the objectives of the educational services.

The quality of the educational process in the institution is determined by the quality of processes and products, the quality of the organizational system and the quality of the services offered to future medical specialists. These three elements are in a strict interdependence and determine the quality of the final product.

The provision of quality educational services in CEMF “Raisa Pacalo” implies the most valid knowledge of the beneficiaries' opinion. One of the indicators of the process of modernization of the study program was the feedback provided by: students, teachers, economic agents and parents, the suggestions of the beneficiaries being discussed and analyzed at the CEIAC meetings and at the meetings of the specialized departments.

The monitoring of the process of implementation of the modernized curriculum included the students' questioning for the purpose of assessing the quality of the process of forming the professional competences within the practical lessons in the specialized subjects. Periodically, the evaluation of the level of satisfaction of the beneficiaries regarding the quality of the practical training process was carried out. In order to constantly improve the psychological climate, the questionnaire regarding the satisfaction of the teachers at the workplace was carried out. In order to optimize the mentoring process, a questionnaire to assess the satisfaction of mentor teachers and beginner teachers was applied, which offered the opportunity to ascertain the degree of integration of young specialists in the activity of CEMF “Raisa Pacalo” and the way of exchanging experience with mentor teachers. In order to know the opinion of the economic agents regarding the quality of the training of the applied competences within the training program, the questionnaire regarding the evaluation of the satisfaction of the economic partners was also carried out.

However, the ones who are mostly responsible for the quality of the educational process are the teachers, but the role of the parents cannot be neglected, in terms of their children's education, and that is why it was opportune to study the way of involving the parents, as well as the relationship that should be one of collaboration with the Center of Excellence. The study addressed a rather important issue, namely the quality of the family involvement in the child's education and the relationship that the family has with the teachers.

The interviews of opinions gave us the opportunity to ascertain the real situation, to elaborate and realize improvement plans for each compartment. The results of the interview were presented by the CEIAC in the teachers' council, the board of directors and the weekly meetings, being followed by concrete decisions to improve the quality of the services offered by the institution.

Among the quality indicators obtained after the implementation of quality management we find:

The level of systematic increase of the quality of students' activity:

- enriching the students' learning experiences through new strategies and learning methods;
- increasing students' performances – academic results, exam results, education for the use of new information and communication technologies.

Increasing the quality of evaluation:

- systematic observation of pupils' activity;
- permanent evaluation of students' performances.

Increasing the quality of the learning environment:

- environment and atmosphere appropriate to the training process;
- purchase of furniture and new equipment.

Increasing the quality of school life:

- the physical and mental safety of the students;
- the quality of the teacher-student relationship;
- access to consultancy and advisory services.

Increasing the level of satisfaction of parents, students and the entire community towards the education offered by the institution:

- increasing the prestige of the institution in the community;
- the level of participation of parents in school life.

Extension of the offer of educational services:

- improvement of personal characteristics – initial training, teaching experience, teaching degrees, career development;
- improving the in-service training of teachers at institutional level through exchange of experience;
- expanding offers of external teacher education.

Increasing the relevance and usefulness of the education offered by CEMF “Raisa Pacalo” for the present and future needs of future medical specialists:

- raising the level of autonomy and responsibility of students for their own learning – students are “taught to learn”;

- increasing the percentage of graduates who continue their studies in the field of medicine;
- increasing the percentage of graduates who are employed.

In conclusion, in this chapter we revealed that, based on an efficient management of quality in education, it is possible, through joint efforts, to carry out an efficient strategic planning process.

Context analysis

In the sphere of institutional strategic planning, context analysis is required, not so much by its theoretical justifications, but especially as a pragmatic requirement. CEMF “Raisa Pacalo” through its mission, is a strongly socially anchored institution, which must and can be in the direct service of the community. The community and, in a broader sense, the context constitutes a very important resource potential in all aspects: human, financial, material, which must be attracted and capitalized by the institution through the offer that, in turn, it proposes to the community. The identification and description of the community and of the interest groups is necessary, given that a good analysis in this field will generate an easier integration of the graduates in the society.

The analysis of the need and demand for education for individuals, groups and the community reveals that, under the pressure of reforming education, the educational market must be expanded and become competitive in almost all its segments.

According to data from European vocational education and training policies, around 50% of new jobs in the European Union are expected to require people who have completed higher education and around 40% will be for those with professional skills, obtained in vocational education and training.

Political environment

Technical vocational education in the Republic of Moldova is regulated by the current documents that ensure the legislative and normative framework for functioning. The government’s policy offer in the field of education is built around the following major objectives:

- equal and increased access to education;
- high quality of education and preparation for life in a knowledge-based society;
- decentralization and depoliticization of the educational system;
- transforming education into the basic resource of state modernization;
- considering the investment in human capital as the most profitable investment in the long run;
- effective combination of elite education with general education;
- institutional development of lifelong learning.

The opportunities created by the educational policy supported by the government for our institution are related to the provision of the necessary facilities through government programs, through the access to international programs, the development of education in the native language, the design of a modern system of assessment of competences, through the diversification of teaching methods and practices, the shifting of the emphasis from the informative to the formative character, the introduction of contemporary forms of international cooperation, etc.

In the context of signing, stamping, adopting and ratifying by the EU member states the Association Agreement with the EU, the Republic of Moldova transposes into the national system of vocational training the approaches of education and training in the medical field, specific to the European area, which can be found in the national legislative and normative documents, including: the Education Code of the Republic of Moldova (2014); Education Strategy 2020; The program for the development of medical and pharmaceutical education in the Republic of Moldova for the years 2011-2020; National Health Policy of the Republic of Moldova for the years 2007-2021; The strategy for the development of the health system in the period 2008-2017; Health Strategy 2020. In accordance with the provisions of the European Nurses Forum Guide for the implementation of Article 31 of the EU Directive 2013/55, it was ensured the transposition into national legislation of the educational requirements for nurses and midwives, by updating the general and specific competences of the Educational Standards, Study Plan and curricula according to the 6 key competences proposed by EFN (European Federation of Nurses).

- ✓ Culture, ethics and values to be ruled upon;
- ✓ Health promotion;

- ✓ Decision making;
- ✓ Communication and teamwork;
- ✓ Research, development and leadership;
- ✓ Nursing care (education and theoretical training);
- ✓ Nursing care (education and practical/clinical training).

At the moment, there is no national legislative framework on the Nurses and Midwives Act, Occupational Standards in the field.

Economic environment

At national level, according to statistical data, the general trend regarding the evolution of the labor force was represented in the last years by the decrease of the employed population and the increase of the unemployment rate. The annual reports of the National Employment Association (NEA) demonstrate the difficulties faced by graduates of secondary, post-secondary, non-tertiary education in integrating into the labour market. The financial legislation allows the attraction of extra-budgetary funds at the level of the institution. At the same time, the interest of economic agents in granting sponsorships or donations to technical vocational education institutions is often low.

According to the World Health Organization study, more than 20 percent of medical staff in Moldova have left the health system in recent years. The data of a recent study conducted by WHO show that about 2000 nurses leave annually the Republic of Moldova to work abroad. A large part of the medical specialists chooses to work in the European Union countries, for better salaries and more attractive working conditions. Consequently, the Republic of Moldova is facing an acute shortage of medical specialists, especially in rural areas.

The effect of these economic factors can be extremely serious, from high disinterest and absenteeism to early school leaving. There is a positive effect in this context expressed by the expansion of social programs in the field: granting social aid scholarships; various projects and programs with local and international budgeting, etc.

Social environment

At the demographic level, there is a continuous decrease of the school population, with long-term effects on the entire education system. The approach of social problems is made with increasing seriousness at national and local level, there are special programs to combat delinquency, drugs, alcoholism, poverty, unemployment, and the upward evolution of the economy is an effective means of combating and remedying social problems.

The migration phenomenon, generated by the inadequate policy and the lack of a National Strategy for stopping and preventing, conditions the breaking of the parents' connection with the school, which affects the quality of this partnership. The rooting of social vices, such as protectionism and corruption, seriously affects citizens' trust in state institutions. The fact that the principles and values of group interests are supported, a large part of the graduates do not want internal employment, so the investments made in education, in general and in our institution, in particular, are absorbed by other beneficiaries from outside.

Technological environment

The analysis of the technological context is on the agenda, due to the fact that technology can bring a substantial increase of quality and efficiency to the educational process. The endowment with computers, the access to the Internet, to virtual libraries or to institutional networks are decisive for the development of educational institutions. The technological context positively influences the structure of the study programs, the quality of the educational process and implicitly the quality of the graduates.

The continuous development worldwide and the emergence of digital technologies in education and in the medical sphere involves a change of mentality at the level of management and provision of services in order to be attractive and to maintain us in the top of technical vocational education in Moldova. Without highly technological equipment and without permanent training of teachers, who can operate in state-of-the-art information systems, the graduate's training will not correspond to the current requirements.

Although the increasing introduction of computer equipment and new technologies is noted, the technological level of education is still low. One cannot talk about the existence of means of distance education (Tele-medicine, online lessons, etc.) to be made available to the medical community. The only places relatively adequately equipped from a technological point of view are in educational institutions.

Ecological environment

At national level, among the priority areas are the Environmental Protection Program and the Program for promoting healthy lifestyles. This direction is about how school projects will promote state policies. As a result of intense urbanization, pollution levels are increasing. Also, little money is allocated to programmes for the protection of the environment and the conservation of flora and fauna. Thus, environmental education must become a priority and an active component in the education of the young generation. Nevertheless, more and more emphasis is placed on the realization and implementation of ecological projects and on the production of natural building materials, which are compatible with the biological and vital rhythms of the planet and man in general.

In response to the priority problems identified and prioritized based on **the SWOT** analysis, carried out with all educational actors, with the involvement of partners, highlighted the following solutions for the strategic development period 2017-2021:

Institutional management:

- motivating the manifestation of the cooperative spirit of the institution's employees;
- preparation of internal documents regulating the activity of the Center of Excellence in Medicine and Pharmacy “Raisa Pacalo”;
- development of quality management at all levels and subdivisions of the institution by developing quality culture;
- efficient and responsible implementation of the strategic development plan of the institution.

Human Resure:

- concern for the professional and pedagogical improvement of the teaching staff of CEMF “Raisa Pacalo” and the assigned medical colleges;
- moral and material stimulation of the institution’s employees on the basis of performance indicators;
- increasing the percentage of insurance with titular teachers.

Educational services for beneficiaries:

- orientation towards competitiveness and performance for integration in the circuit of national and international medical professional values;
- providing course units with the curriculum (modular and disciplinary);
- providing curricular tools, educational soffts of the educational process;
- stimulating a participatory educational process, which would involve students in making decisions regarding didactic, extra-teaching and cultural activities;
- promoting the organizational culture at the level of all the subdivisions of the Center of Excellence;
- ensuring the continuity of respect for institutional and national traditions.

Technical-material basis:

- reconstruction of the central block of studies;
- establishment and endowment of the modern simulation center for the formation, development and evaluation of the professional competences of the students from the Center of Excellence and from the assigned medical colleges.

Partnership:

- promoting the student-teacher-parent partnership;
- strengthening an efficient feed-back system both at the level of the institution’s employees, students and the economic environment;
- coordination of the methodical activity and continuous training of the teaching and managerial staff of the assigned medical colleges in partnership with the in-service training institutions;
- harmonization of the international cooperation activities of CEMF “Raisa Pacalo” with the policies of development of the international partnership of the Ministry of Health and the Ministry of Education and Research of the Moldova Publishing House, in order to stimulate the academic mobility of teachers and students.

The strategic development directions, designed, focused on the following aspects:

1. Modernising the training curricula of medical specialists with post-secondary professional education from the perspective of labour market needs in accordance with the national qualifications framework;
2. Ensuring the implementation of the modernized curricula, connected to the needs of the beneficiaries;

3. Ensuring the educational process with professional, competitive and competent teaching and managerial staff;
4. Creating a democratic, formative, individualized, stimulating and sensitive learning environment to the individual needs of the beneficiaries;
5. Ensuring the quality of the practical training process by developing and developing sustainable partnerships with national and international medical institutions;
6. Promoting an institutional performance management, participatory, complex and systemic approached, connected to the needs of the educational community, able to ensure the achievement of the mission and strategic objectives of CEMF "Raisa Pacalo";
7. Creating an institutional system for monitoring and improving the quality of the educational process;
8. Ensuring the methodological and methodical assistance of the assigned medical colleges.

According to the activity reports for the analyzed strategic development period, it was found that the strategic targets set were achieved, including through:

- elaboration and approval of educational standards for the qualifications: Medical Assistant, Community Nurse, Epidemiologist Hygienist Nurse, Laboratory Diagnostic Nurse, Midwife, Pharmacist Assistant, Dental Technician;
- updating and approving the Educational Standards to the qualifications: Nurse, Community Nurse, Epidemiologist Hygienist Nurse, Laboratory Diagnostic Nurse, Midwife, Pharmacist Assistant, Dental Technician;
- expanding the educational offer by introducing the system of training nurses through dual education;
- upgrading the curriculum to all specialties and qualifications;
- promoting the initial training of medical specialists from the perspective of student centering, IT capitalization and sustainable training of professional competences;
- providing the modernized curriculum with curricular tools: textbooks, course supports, guides for practical lessons, item collections, protocols/ algorithms of practical skills, educational software, webinars, tutorials, electronic platforms, etc.;
- continuous increase of the level of professionalism of the teacher by supporting the didactic and scientific degrees;
- the consistent promotion of the CE values and traditions by carrying out the didactic, extra-teaching and extracurricular activities relevant to the needs and expectations of teachers and pupils;
- development of the institutional system of quality management with the annual realization of the internal management control and ensuring the decisional transparency regarding the activity of the institution, including through accessible information sources;
- national and international cooperation in the fields of teaching activity, scientific research, academic mobility, creation of partnerships in order to harmonize the CE cooperation activities with national and international partners.

The most visible achievements the institution has demonstrated in the fields of:

- training, validation and certification of the professional competences of the graduates of the institutions in the medical vocational education in the country;
- the didactic, curricular and methodological assurance of the medical vocational education;
- coordination and methodological guidance of the assigned medical colleges;
- in-service training of teachers in the professional medical system;
- career guidance and promotion of non-tertiary post-secondary medical education at national and international level.

Among the persistent issues, remaining for the next period, 2021-2026, are:

- updating occupational profiles, occupational and educational standards, study plans and modular/disciplinary curricula;
- optimizing the number of subjects per semester in the New Study Plans from 12-14 to 8 and diversifying the offer of optional subjects by choosing the subject from 3-4 proposed subjects;
- diversification of the educational offer by implementing studies in the *specialty of Patient Care*, qualification *Medical Assistant in Medical Emergencies*, including in dual education at the qualifications: *Medical Assistant in Dentistry*, *Pharmacist Assistant*, *Dental Technician*;

- accreditation of the Department of continuous training of teachers and managers of medical colleges and continuous professional training programs.

Conclusions and perspectives

In conclusion, according to the set of process, product and result indicators, applied in the process of internal and external monitoring and evaluation of the SDP, of the institution's activity, we find that the specific objectives designed for each year, in the operational plan of activity, were achieved in the proposed terms, according to the agreed methodology, with the resources expected in a proportion of 90 percent. The management team, in partnership with all educational actors and CEMF partners, ensured the necessary conditions for achieving the objectives, at a higher level of quality.

The results obtained by our students can be characterized, summarily, as a continuous increase in the degree of competitiveness of the future specialists trained in the Center of Excellence. The degree of satisfaction of students and parents regarding the training process is high, being confirmed by the results of multiple surveys.

The data collected in the monitoring and evaluation process demonstrate the involvement in the process of achieving performance by students and employees, transparency of decision-making and democratic management of human, material and financial resources.

Moreover, after assessing the results, we can highlight that the impact of the Center of Excellence can be evaluated by the role of the institution in the provision of the healthcare system with medical specialists with secondary education, and in the continuous training of teachers in medical colleges in the country, as well as by the role of the institution in promoting vocational medical education at national and international level.

The lessons learned by the management team demonstrate that only the strategic planning of the activity of the subdivisions of the institution, and of the institution as a whole, ensures the consecutive and prosperous development of both the educational institution and the vocational medical education system at national level. Thus, we consider that the analyzed SDP fully reflected the educational policy of the country and the needs of the beneficiaries, and through the development of the institution, it ensured their achievement. This document promoted a management based on the culture of quality and created adequate conditions for the proper functioning of the institution, but also for its continuous development.

References:

1. Planul de dezvoltare strategică al CEMF „Raisa Pacalo”, 2016-2021. Available: <https://cemf.md/pages/index/Transparena-decizional-Planurile-de-dezvoltare-startegica> [Accessed: 22.02.2022]
2. CHINĂ, R. Managementul organizației școlare Proiectul de Dezvoltare Instituțională (PDI) planificare, elaborare, implementare, evaluare, îmbunătățire. București: Universitaria, 2019. 194 p. ISBN 978-606-28-1021-4
3. Planificarea strategică. Available: <http://www.businessdictionary.com/definition/strategic-planning.html> [Accessed: 02.03.2022]
4. BEZEDE, R. (coord.) *Elaborarea planului de dezvoltare strategică a instituției*. Chișinău: PRO DIDACTICA, 2017. 62 p. ISBN 978-9975-3177-1-9
5. DEBB, G. *The Top 6 Steps Of Strategic Planning*, Available: <https://www.forbes.com/sites/georgedeeb/2018/12/04/the-top-6-steps-of-strategic-planning/> [Accessed: 22.02.2022]
6. GORAȘ-POSTICĂ, V. Noi realități și provocări ale educației interculturale în universități. Studiu de analiză a necesităților pe marginea documentelor de planificare strategică. În: *Didactica PRO...*, 2021, nr.3 (127), p.17-22. ISSN 1810-6455

Author's data:

Viorica GORAȘ-POSTICĂ, dr.habilitatus, professor, Moldova State University.

E-mail: vgoras@yahoo.com

ORCID: 0000-0001-9096-621X

Svetlana CHEPTANARI, PhD student, CEMF „Raisa Pacalo”.

E-mail: svetlana.cheptanari@mail.ru

ORCID: 0000-0003-4694-6224

Mariana NEGREAN, PhD student, CEMF „Raisa Pacalo”.

E-mail: m.negrean777@gmail.com

ORCID: 0000-0002-7865-4747

Presented on 15.03.2022